

Mathematical competencies in understanding and using an industrial guideline on motion design

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Abstract

Mathematical competence is used in the SEFI MSIG curriculum document (Alpers et al. 2013) to specify curricular goals. It emphasizes the ability to understand and use mathematics in relevant situations and contexts. In order to identify goals, application subjects and later workplaces should be investigated. This contribution analyses the mathematical competencies needed when using an industrial guideline on motion design issued by the German Association of Engineers (VDI) which is widely used by practising engineers and thus provides insights into real usage of mathematics beyond a single workplace. Potential educational consequences and learning opportunities are also discussed.

Introduction

SEFI's Maths Special Interest Group bases its curriculum document (Alpers et al. 2013) on the concept of mathematical competence and competencies as developed by Niss and Hojgaard (Niss/Hojgaard 2019). The overarching goal is the ability to do, use and understand mathematical concepts relevant in engineering situations and contexts which is further specified by identifying eight competence areas called mathematical competencies like mathematical reasoning, problem solving and modelling. There are two main sources for finding meaningful goals within these areas: application subjects of the study course under consideration where mathematical concepts are used for modelling and problem solving; and usage of mathematics at real engineering workplaces. For investigating the latter, different methods including interviews, observations and analysis of artefacts have been used (for an overview see Alpers 2021). When visiting single workplaces it is always questionable to which extent the results can be generalized. In this contribution I analyse a specific guideline on motion design issued by the German Association of Engineers (VDI). Motion design is a standard task in mechanical engineering, and the VDI Guideline 2143 (VDI 2024) is often used and supported in controller software. Therefore, the guideline offers the opportunity to get information of mathematical competencies needed by a larger group of engineers in a broad spectrum of companies without claiming that every engineer needs to have the competencies. In the next section I give a brief overview of the structure and content of the guideline. The subsequent section analyses the required mathematical competencies. Finally, educational consequences and learning opportunities are discussed.

VDI Guideline 2143 – An overview

The VDI Guideline 2143 supports the definition of suitable one-dimensional motion functions where the dependent variable has the meaning of distance or angle and the independent variable may be distance, angle or time. In a slider-crank mechanism (see Alpers 2015) the driving element is a motor and the driven element is a slider, so the function has the meaning of distance over angle or distance over time. The guideline

abstracts from the concrete mechanical situation by considering a function $y(x)$ allowing for all meaningful combinations. In VDI 2143 the overall motion task is subdivided into sections and the boundary points of sections are classified as rest (R) ($y' = y'' = 0$), constant velocity (G) ($y' \neq 0, y'' = 0$), turn-over (U) ($y' = 0, y'' \neq 0$) and general motion (B) ($y' \neq 0, y'' \neq 0$). The user sets up a so-called motion plan where the sections are defined (Figure 1) and the values of the derivatives are provided.

Figure 1: Example of a motion plan

There are sixteen types of sections according to the possible combinations of boundary points and hence sixteen types of so-called motion tasks. For RR and GG it is assumed that the velocity is constant between the two points. Each task is transformed into a normed version $f(z)$ by scaling and shifting, such that $f(0)=0, f(1)=1, z=0 \dots 1$ holds (VDI 2024, Formula (12)). For each of the sixteen tasks the guideline provides one or more normed motion functions $f(z)$ which have continuous derivatives up to second order and which allow to fulfil the requirements regarding the boundary points. In order to choose a suitable function from the offering the guideline defines four quality criteria, the maximum absolute values of $f', f'', f''', f' \cdot f''$. These criteria have concrete meaning regarding application features, for example keeping the maximum absolute value of f'' low results in low mass forces at the driven element such that unwanted vibration can be avoided.

For all motion tasks the polynomial of degree 5 can be used since it has six degrees of freedom such that arbitrary boundary conditions up to the second derivative can be fulfilled. Other functions which have better values regarding certain quality criteria are often constructed by piecewise defining the second derivative and developing from that the first derivative and the motion function itself such that the required boundary conditions are fulfilled. As an example we consider for the RR task (“rest-in-rest”) the so-called modified acceleration trapezoid which is shown in figure 2. Here, the second derivative consists of 5 pieces. Because the absolute maximum value can be held

constantly over a non-zero subinterval (as opposed to the polynomial of degree 5 for example), one can keep the maximum lower than when using a polynomial.

Figure 2: Modified acceleration trapezoid from (VDI 2143)

Mathematical competencies in understanding and using VDI 2143

In the following, we use the framework of mathematical competencies (Alpers et al. 2013; Niss/Hojgaard 2019) in order to analyse the mathematical abilities needed in understanding and using the VDI Guideline 2143:

Thinking mathematically: This competency is concerned with having an idea where and in which ways mathematics can play a role. Readers of the guideline should have the expectation that for motion to be realized by a controller it needs to be described in a formal way using mathematical objects like functions or value tables. Having such an expectation helps to get a quick overview of what the guideline provides similarly as a well-founded expectation of what a CAD programme can do helps in getting familiar with another such programme very quickly. Mathematics should also provide means to make judgements on candidates for motion functions, i.e. identify meaningful quantities as quality measures like the characteristic values stated above. Certainly, for a justification of such measures application aspects beyond mathematics must play a role. Readers don't have to bother about mathematical thinking in form of theorems and proofs since a guideline for practitioners is not meant to provide elaborations like academic textbooks.

Reasoning mathematically: The guideline intends to present the state-of-the-art in motion design for ready use by a practitioner without elaborating on the derivation and reasoning behind all the results stated. Therefore, in general only results are given in form of formulae. For example, motion functions are stated together with the first two derivatives but how one gets from the second derivative depicted in figure 2 (modified acceleration trapezoid) to the function itself is not explained since this is assumed to be part of the standard mathematical repertoire of the reader. This also holds for switching between the original and the normed version of a motion law by shifting and scaling a function. Explanations are given when it comes to the meaning of the characteristic values. E.g., the maximum kinetic energy at the driven element is stated as $E_{max,kin} = \frac{m_{ab}}{2} \left(\frac{Y_{ij}}{T_{ij}} \cdot C_v \right)^2$ (Formula (36) in (VDI 2143) with $C_v = \max |f'(z)|$), hence the characteristic value C_v should be kept low for energy efficiency reasons.

No reasoning is provided as to why a certain function gives a low value for one of the characteristic values. In the modified acceleration trapezoid (Figure 2), for example, the possibility to keep the maximum value over a whole interval (and not just at a single point as is the case with the polynomial of degree 5) allows for a lower maximum value. The reader does not need this reasoning but can just choose the motion law for its low maximum of the second derivative. Only when a reader is not content with what the guideline provides and tries to set up a motion function on his own could such a line of reasoning be very valuable.

The symbolic expressions for the motion laws contain a lot of symbols (e.g. for the boundary values or for parameters) such that the reader must think about which quantities are given by the application task and which ones can be set freely. With several motion functions there is one degree of freedom which can be used to set a parameter occurring in the function or to prescribe a resulting characteristic value within certain limits. Capturing the limits also requires some reasoning because square roots occurring within the expressions must be real.

Problem solving: The guideline is designed to help engineers to solve the problem of constructing a “good” motion function. For this, it provides the section-wise procedure following the problem solving strategy of “divide-and-conquer”. Moreover, for the sections it provides normed function candidates and states quality criteria that can be used for choosing one specific function. The reader still has to make use of the procedure by giving the necessary input in form of points of the motion plan and boundary values of the sections as well as parameter values for some of the functions offered by the guideline. Very often, the application requirements do not prescribe exactly the points in the plan and even for a rest phase small variation might be allowed. Therefore, it is still the task of the reader to modify the motion plan appropriately if the outcome of the current plan is still unsatisfactory, e.g. because the overall cycle time is too large.

Mathematical modelling: As opposed to many other modelling problems, motion design is not mainly concerned with analysis, but with synthesis. The guideline already provides the central initial mathematical model for doing this in form of the motion plan. The reader still has to clarify the situation at hand in order to find out about boundary conditions and their strictness. The guideline contains several motion laws for each subtask to choose from and it states characteristic values as a quality measure to justify the choice. Still, the reader has to investigate the specifics of the application situation in order to judge on the relative importance of the different characteristic values. The characteristic values might be too coarse since they do not give information on where the maximum occurs which might be important for the consequences. Moreover, the reader has to validate the resulting motion function and check whether it is within the limits given by the application (e.g. the required power of the driving motor is not too large making the device too expensive).

Representing mathematical entities: The main mathematical objects dealt with in the guideline are symbols and functions. The symbol table has 89 entries. For motion functions the abstract representation $y(x)$ is used because x can be time, distance or angle and y can be distance or angle. The functions are given in a normed version $f(z)$ as stated in the previous section. The functions are often piecewise defined functions where the

pieces are presented giving an expression and a sub-domain. When there are symmetries, the representation is shortened by referencing a former piece, e.g. $f_4(z) = -f_3(1 - z)$. For several functions also graphical representations are given showing the function pieces (mainly regarding the second derivative as in Figure 2). The reader has to connect these representations by discovering the sine and polynomial pieces in the figures. The figures also help the reader by giving graphical meaning to parameters and characteristic values and by providing tables of graphical representations of functions offered for a certain sub-task (like RR: rest-in-rest); the reader can easily recognize the differences and make his choice. There are also graphical representations on how characteristic values vary with parameter values appearing in a motion function. This way the reader gets an overview of how all characteristic values depend on the parameter such that he can achieve an adequate combination of characteristic values.

Handling mathematical symbols and formalism: Handling symbols and understanding and using symbolic expressions is very important for understanding and using the guideline. If the reader does not have algebraic fluency and familiarity with understanding and manipulating symbolic expressions he still is able to take the expressions and type them into a software tool for further processing but even then the correct usage of brackets is still left up to the user. The understanding is much deeper when the role of the symbols within the expressions is recognized. Readers should also be able to switch between the symbolic representation of a function piece for a section and its normalized version ($f(z)$, $z=0..1$). For some parameterized functions it is helpful when the reader can analyse expression with roots in order to choose parameter values which result in real values. Readers should also understand the sine and polynomial expressions in order to connect them to the corresponding pieces in the graphical representations. Often, the characteristic values are also given as symbolic expressions such that the reader can see how the value depends on the “ingredients”. Sometimes, this is not possible because the respective equations cannot be solved symbolically such that the value can only be calculated for a concrete numerical configuration. The reader should be familiar with such a situation and should not always expect symbolic expressions. For the task BB among the suggested functions there are also B-Splines. These are defined recursively and symbolic expressions are given how to choose the control vector in order to fulfil the boundary conditions.

Communicating mathematically: VDI guidelines are not meant to replace academic textbooks and hence they contain very “condensed” knowledge on state-of-the-art methods. They lack the broad explanations and elaborations of the latter. The reader has to capture the procedure of setting up the motion function section by section by transforming the sub-tasks into a normalized form and choosing motion function from a set of suggested ones using characteristic values. The practising engineers does not have to understand everything in the guideline but he has to recognize which information is expected from him and which kind of results he gets. He must capture which parts must be really understood and which can just be used. He might also have a software tool provided with the controller which enables him to set up the motion plan and make choices when the functions of the guideline are implemented there. The reader might also have the duty to document his work using the motion plan with boundary conditions and to justify the choice of functions based on the characteristic values.

Using aids and tools: There are different ways of making use of the information provided by the guideline using technological tools. An engineer might create a value table using the function pieces taken from the guideline using for example a spreadsheet programme. He might also use controller software to build the function there without having to implement anything further. If none of the function pieces offered by the guideline is suitable an engineer might still use the suggested section-wise procedure and construct his own motion pieces. For investigating such pieces a mathematical programme could be very helpful (setting up and plotting functions, computing derivatives, solving equations).

Educational consequences and learning opportunities

The results of the above analysis can be used in several ways. They might corroborate the justification of competencies which are already part of the curriculum. For example, a certain degree of algebraic fluency is quite important for students not to be overwhelmed by the plethora of symbolic mathematics used in the guideline. One can also draw good motivation scenarios from the material, e.g. for shifting and scaling functions or for concepts like continuity and differentiability when one uses piecewise defined functions. Students see that all the basic topics on functions really occur in serious work on application questions which might increase their readiness to look for applicability of things they learnt in mathematics. Moreover, the results might give reason to identify additional aspects like the constructive use of functions which gives deeper insights into their modelling properties. The guideline is also helpful when finding assignments or projects for students which provide opportunities for acquiring the competencies needed for understanding and using the guideline (cf. Alpers 2014; Alpers 2015). For students particularly interested in programming one might even let them implement a development environment for the guideline in Maple® and Matlab®.

References

- Alpers, B. et al. (2013). A framework for mathematics curricula in engineering education. Brussels: SEFI.
- Alpers, B. (2014). A Mathematics Curriculum for a Practice-oriented Study Course in Mechanical Engineering, Aalen: Aalen University.
- Alpers, B. (2015). Mathematical learning opportunities in motion design problems, in: Hibberd, S., Lawson, D., Robinson, C. (Eds.) Proc. 8th IMA Conference on Mathematical Education of Engineers, Loughborough University.
- Alpers, B. (2021). Making Sense of Engineering Workplace Mathematics to Inform Engineering Mathematics Education. A Report for the Mathematics Interest Group. Brussels: SEFI.
- Niss, M., Hojgaard, T. (2019). Mathematical competencies revisited. Educational Studies in Mathematics 102, pp. 9-28.
- VDI (2024). Richtlinie/Guideline 2143: Bewegungsgesetze für Kurvengetriebe und Motion-Control-Systeme, Theoretische Grundlagen – Motion rules for cam mechanisms and motion control systems, Theoretical fundamentals, Berlin: Beuth.